

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE CONCEPT OF THE SAFE FUNCTIONING OF THE COUNTRY'S NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Abstract

The article discusses the problem of ensuring the economic security of the country. The essence of the traditional approach to ensuring the economic security of the country outlined, as well as a set of measures of the European Commission to strengthen the economic security of the European Union bloc as a whole.

Since the existing paradigms do not allow us to identify possible emerging economic threats in the future, both for an individual country and for the EU bloc as a whole, a different approach needed to identify and eliminate emerging economic threats in the future.

The article proposes an alternative conceptual approach - the concept of the safe functioning of the national economy. The basic principles of the concept of safe functioning of the national economy as a dynamic system set out.

Keywords: national economy of the country, functioning of the national economy, cyclical nature of functioning, stages of functioning, dynamic stability of functioning, stage of the emergence of threats, forecasting the emergence of threats.

Methodology

The research methodology consists of historical and comparative analysis, as well as a systematic approach.

In the article from a historical perspective set out paradigms for ensuring the economic security of the country from the 17th century to the present, both by Eurasian economists and government agencies of the countries of the post-Soviet space and the European Union.

The alternative concept we propose for ensuring the economic security of the country - "the concept of the safe functioning of the country's national economy" is set out as a system, the elements of which are four main basic principles.

Introduction

There is a history of the development of theoretical, methodological and conceptual foundations for the functioning of the country's economic systems. Published scientific studies explain the various mechanisms of the functioning of the national economy, formed at certain stages of human history. The Austrian economist I. P. Schumpeter, having conducted research from antiquity to the mid-17th century, concluded that the works written on the country's economy did not have scientific theoretical and methodological features, but were pamphlets of ideas and thoughts. [1, 2]

In the 17th and 18th centuries, European countries were published works related to the economic security of a country. In the published works, the authors connected the economic security of their countries with the superiority of the economic potential of their own country over the economic potential of a neighboring country, as well as more efficient use of the factors of the country's economic potential. With regard to increasing the wealth of one's own state in foreign trade, the authors in the articles proposed a system of rules that would increase exports of domestically produced goods by reducing imports from a neighboring country. The

provisions of A. Smith's absolute economic advantages and D. Ricardo's relative economic advantages in competition with neighboring states form the basis of the modern theory of international trade of Swedish economists Huckster and Olin, as well as the American economist, Nobel Prize laureate V. Leontief. [3, 4, 5, 6]

Discussion

Paradigms of "economic security of the country"

The reason why one country achieves an advantage in economic competition over another country is ultimately ends with the national wealth of a country that is economically weak in competition flowing to a country that is economically strong in competition. In this case, the level of well-being of the population of a country that is weak in economic competition becomes lower than the level of well-being of the population of a strong country. This reason causes a decrease in the trust of the population of economically weak countries in their state. To prevent this mistrust, each state is trying to bring its economy to a competitive level.

Ensuring the country's military, social and political security requires strengthening the country's economy. Because of one country's economy, being stronger than another country's the economically strong country's wealth increases. A rich country provides a healthier and more prosperous life for its people. The population of a prosperous country trusts the state they have created and constantly defends their state from the interference of foreign states, as well as from threats arising from internal unrest. An economically stronger country with a stronger military potential will more effectively organize the country's defense against military intervention by foreign states.

The growth of the country's economic power is possible if the factors of the country's economic potential are effectively used its territory, natural and climatic conditions and reserves of raw materials, the

means of production available in the country, the country's labor and monetary reserves.

In the late 80s and 90s of the last century, in connection with the emergence of the new independent states of Eastern Europe and the states of the post-Soviet space, solving the problem of the country's economic security became one of the main tasks of the governments of these countries

Economists in the post-Soviet countries are trying to determine the socio-economic threats to the state based on the methodology of "threshold security indicators" proposed by Russian scientists. [7].

However, a study of the economic security situation in dozens of countries around the world using the methodology of "threshold indicators of economic security" showed the inconsistency of this methodology. [8].

Among the concepts of "country economic security" proposed by economists in post-Soviet countries, there are approaches related to the illegal form conducting economic activities in the country.

In international practice, the behind-the-scenes part of a country's economic system called the non-observable economy, from the point of view of statistical accounting.

Among the concepts of "economic security of the country" proposed by economists in post-Soviet countries, there are approaches associated with the illegal (secret) form of economic activity in the country. In international practice, the behind-the-scenes part of a country's economic system, from a statistical point of view, called the non-observable economy.

There are two main reasons why a certain part of economic activity is hidden: despite the fact that it is prohibited by the laws of the country, the activity is carried out in an illegal manner; conducting business secretly to avoid paying taxes and social benefits, despite the fact that it is not permitted by law.

In official government documents of the Russian Federation and CIS countries, the category of economic security interpreted as the ability of the country's economy to provide a decent life and development for citizens; socio-economic and military-political stability of the state and society; as well as the ability to withstand internal and external threats. [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18]

Unlike the state of the Russian Federation and the CIS countries, in the USA and in Western European countries, as well as in Japan, the economic security of the country considered primarily in the context of industrial espionage and in the context of foreign economic relations. [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27].

At the beginning of 2024, the European Commission presented a package of measures to strengthen the economic security of the European Union in the context of growing geopolitical tensions in general. The package of documents proposes to take measures in five directions: strengthening the verification of foreign investments in the EU; identifying security risks associated with EU investments in third countries; increasing the effectiveness of

control over the export of dual-use goods; improving research safety in the EU; strengthening support for the development of dual-use technologies. [28]

Conclusions

In our opinion, the above approaches to the category "economic security of the country" are in the nature of identifying facts of threats in the past. These approaches cannot predict a country's future economic security. Without a vision of possible threats in the future, it is impossible to prepare a timely program for implementing measures to prevent and neutralize these threats.

We propose a different concept for ensuring the economic security of the country - the concept of the safe functioning of the country's national economy.

The concept of "safe functioning of the country's national economy" that we propose as an alternative to the concept of "economic security of the country" has a different essence and content. The main provisions of the "concept for the safe functioning of the national economy" include the following.

Concept of "safe functioning of the country's national economy"

Thus, the safe functioning of the national economy of the country must be carried out by the state of the country. The government of the country, by preparing regulatory forecasts of possible emerging threats in the national economy in the future, can prevent these threats. And for this, the government must draw up an appropriate program to prevent possible threats in the future.

1. The national economic system is the basis of the state structure.

The economic system of a country forms the basis of any government structure, regardless of the form of government structure. The government, as the highest institution of the state superstructure, considered as a subject of management that ensures the dynamic activity of the national economy. The main task of the government as a superstructure of public administration is to organize the safe and effective functioning of the national economy in accordance with the national interests of the country.

We believe that the military, political and social security of the country achieved by ensuring the safe functioning of the country's national economy.

If there is a possibility of external or internal threats to the activities of the national economy of the country and these threats can be prevented in advance, then the country's national economy will function safely, ensuring military, political and social security.

The safe functioning of the country's national economic system characterized by a continuous increase in the volume of Y products produced and services provided. In this case, the volume of total income G_1 received in the country at time t_1 is greater than the volume G_0 of total income received at time t_0 : $G_1 > G_0$.

A result of an increase in the amount of total income G_1 in the national economy at time t_1 , the volume of taxes and fees T_1 paid to the state budget exceeds the amount of taxes and fees T_0 paid to the state budget at time t_0 . In connection with the increase in tax and duty payments to the state budget, the authorities are increasing the costs of maintaining the state, including the

costs of protecting the country from military aggression, and raising the country's military security to a higher level.

Also, by increasing taxes and fees T_1 paid to the state budget at time t_1 , the authorities can achieve a more effective solution to the social problems of the country's population, and social security is ensured in the country.

Thus, the safe functioning of the country's national economy is a factor ensuring the military, political and social security of the country. The safe functioning of the national economy ensures the military, political and social security of the state.

II. Balanced and sustainable functioning of the national economy.

In the general theory of systems, the equilibrium of a system explained as the ability of a system to maintain its previous state for an indefinitely long time when internal and external forces appear that act on the system. [29].

The functioning of the national economy, due to its dynamic nature, has the characteristic of sustainability. The stability of dynamic systems explained as the ability of a system to lose its equilibrium state, as result of the influence of internal or external forces, and after their elimination - the ability of the system to restore its equilibrium state without destruction. However, it should be noted, that if the national economy as a dynamic system does not have appropriate stability, then it, having lost its equilibrium state, collapse, as happened with the economy of the USSR.

III. The cyclical nature of the functioning of the national economy in the long-term (over 30 years) period.

In the long term (30 years and above), the activity of the national economic system has a cyclical characteristic consisting of four stages: development, development slowdown; stagnation (crisis); recession and stabilization.

The development stage of the period is accompanied by an increase in investments in the country's economy, an increase in the exchange rates of stocks and securities, an increase in the production volume of products, a decrease in unemployment in the country, an increase in the profits of enterprises and organizations, as well as the population's monetary income.

The crisis stage is characterized by a decrease in the efficiency of investments, a decrease in the growth rate of production volumes, a lack of available jobs in providing employment to the population and the emergence of unemployment, rising product prices and the formation of inflationary processes in the national economy of the country and is accompanied by the emergence of similar negative economic phenomena.

The activity of the national economy during the recession is characterized by a very low utilization rate of manufacturing enterprises, a rapid decline in production volumes, a decrease in employment and an increase in unemployment, a decrease in investment in the national economy, depreciation of the country's currency and a rapid increase in product prices. The bankruptcy of enterprises in many cases is

accompanied by a partial destruction of productive forces and the emergence of similar negative economic situations and economic processes.

At the stage of development of the national economy, the formation of any threats from within the system is usually not expected. At this stage, threats arise only as a result of economic expansion from outside the country.

In the activities of the national economy, threats from within the system begin to form at the end of the development stage - at the stage of continuous decline in the growth of production volumes. At this stage, in order to prevent threats arising from within the system, measures are taken to prevent these threats by implementing appropriate interventions in the functioning mechanism of the national economy.

IV. Management of threats arising in the activities of the national economy of the country

Managing the activities of dynamic systems includes, first of all, the stage of drawing up normative forecasts of the system's activity in the future period and making decisions on the functioning of the national economy in the future period based on the forecasts.

We believe that the state can ensure the safe functioning of the country's national economy and prevent emerging threats by creating a management system to prevent these threats.

Thus, the safe functioning of the country's national economy is carried out by the state, preparing normative forecasts of possible emerging threats in the national economy and drawing up an appropriate program to prevent possible threats.

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